

Mixed ligand complexes of alkaline earth metals. Part-XIV. Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} complexes with 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde and salicylaldehyde or hydroxyaromatic ketones

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Reactions of Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} chlorides with two carbonyl compounds (HL and HL') in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratios in ethanol have yielded mixed ligand complexes of the type [MLL'(H₂O)₂] (where M = Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} and Ba^{II}; HL = 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde and HL' = salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyacetophenone, 2-hydroxypropiophenone or 2-hydroxybenzophenone). These complexes have been characterized by elemental analyses, TLC, IR and ¹H NMR spectra.

In continuation of our earlier work on mixed ligand complexes of alkaline earth metals¹, in the present paper the mixed ligand complexes of the type [MLL'(H₂O)₂] (where M = Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} or Ba^{II}; HL = 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde (5-NO₂salH); HL' = salicylaldehyde (salH), 2-hydroxyacetophenone (hapH), 2-hydroxypropiophenone (hppH) or 2-hydroxybenzophenone (hbpH) are described.

Results and discussion

The reactions of the metal ions with 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde and salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyacetophenone, 2-hydroxypropiophenone or 2-hydroxybenzophenone in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratios result in the formation of mixed ligand complexes (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Synthesis of mixed ligand complexes.

The resulting mixed ligand complexes have been isolated as yellow solids. They are insoluble in most of the organic solvents such as methanol, ethanol, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and n-hexane but soluble in DMF and DMSO. Most of these complexes decompose on heating at higher temperatures. The molar conductances of the complexes are very low indicating their non-electrolytic nature. Presence of two coordinated water molecules in the mixed ligand complexes of alkaline earth metals with similar ligands has been established by TGA studies². The characteristics and analyses of the complexes are recorded in Table 1. The metal atom appears to be hexa-coordinated in these complexes and the probable geometry may be octahedral³.

TLC of all the mixed ligand complexes and the corresponding bis-complexes was performed on silica gel G using a benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 1, v/v) mixture as the solvent. Spots on the TLC plates were detected by iodine vapours. Mixed ligand complexes showed a single spot with the R_f value being the intermediate of the two corresponding bis-complexes. This indicates that they are mixed ligand complexes rather than a mixture of the two bis-complexes.

Infrared spectra :

In the IR spectra of the mixed ligand complexes of alkaline earth metals the νC=O frequencies are observed at 1600–1660 cm⁻¹. In free 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde, salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyacetophenone, 2-hydroxypropiophenone

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the mixed ligand complexes

Comp.	Colour and Decomp. temp. (°C)	Yield (%)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)			
			Metal	C	H	N
[Mg(5-NO ₂ sal)(sal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow 275	44	6.85 (6.99)	48.32 (48.38)	3.74 (3.76)	4.07 (4.02)
[Mg(5-NO ₂ sal)(hap)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow 278	46	6.60 (6.72)	49.80 (49.82)	4.19 (4.18)	3.85 (3.87)
[Mg(5-NO ₂ sal)(hpp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow 285	48	6.35 (6.47)	51.08 (51.18)	4.52 (4.56)	3.71 (3.73)
[Mg(5-NO ₂ sal)(hbp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow 235	51	5.61 (5.73)	56.70 (56.73)	4.01 (4.04)	3.27 (3.30)
[Ca(5-NO ₂ sal)(sal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow 210	40	11.15 (11.01)	46.11 (46.30)	3.56 (3.60)	3.82 (3.85)
[Ca(5-NO ₂ sal)(hap)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow 270	58	10.51 (10.62)	47.71 (47.78)	3.94 (4.00)	3.70 (3.71)
[Ca(5-NO ₂ sal)(hpp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow 295	46	10.12 (10.24)	49.03 (49.03)	4.32 (4.38)	3.57 (3.58)
[Ca(5-NO ₂ sal)(hbp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow 230	48	9.01 (9.10)	54.61 (54.69)	3.82 (3.90)	3.12 (3.18)
[Sr(5-NO ₂ sal)(sal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow 260	40	21.18 (21.33)	40.91 (40.93)	3.14 (3.18)	3.56 (3.40)
[Sr(5-NO ₂ sal)(hap)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow 265	52	20.45 (20.63)	42.40 (42.42)	3.52 (3.56)	3.21 (3.29)
[Sr(5-NO ₂ sal)(hpp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow 210	38	19.75 (19.97)	43.71 (43.80)	3.87 (3.90)	3.14 (3.19)
[Sr(5-NO ₂ sal)(hbp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow 260	41	17.78 (18.00)	49.32 (49.35)	3.46 (3.51)	2.82 (2.87)
[Ba(5-NO ₂ sal)(sal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow 335	41	29.64 (29.82)	36.48 (36.51)	2.80 (2.84)	3.01 (3.04)
[Ba(5-NO ₂ sal)(hap)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow 325	61	28.74 (28.93)	37.92 (37.98)	3.12 (3.18)	2.91 (2.95)
[Ba(5-NO ₂ sal)(hpp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow 255	50	28.32 (28.10)	39.31 (39.34)	3.46 (3.50)	2.80 (2.86)
[Ba(5-NO ₂ sal)(hbp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow 275	49	25.77 (25.59)	44.71 (44.77)	3.16 (3.18)	2.58 (2.61)

and 2-hydroxybenzophenone bands at 1680, 1660, 1650, 1640 and 1640 cm⁻¹ respectively are observed due to νC=O⁴. Thus these bands shift to lower wave number side in the complexes supporting the coordination of these ligands with the metal ion. Such shifts to lower wave number side on complexation have been reported in the mixed ligand complexes of alkaline earth and transition metals^{1,5}. In case of Mg(sal)₂, Bellamy and Beecher⁶ have reported νC=O bands at 1681 cm⁻¹. Banerjee *et al.*⁷ have reported the νC=O band in free salicylaldehyde at 1700 cm⁻¹ which is shifted to lower frequency region (1600–1650 cm⁻¹) in magnesium complexes Mg(sal)₂(H₂O)₂⁷ and [Mg(sal)₂]₂-dnr⁷ (where dnr = dinitroresorcinol). Banerjee *et al.*⁷ found similar bands due to νC=O at 1600 and 1610 cm⁻¹ in [Ca(sal)₂]₂-dnr and [Ca(onp)₂]₂-dnr (where onp = *o*-nitro-

phenol) respectively. In the mixed ligand complexes, the weak bands in the region 400–550 cm⁻¹ which are absent in the free ligands may be assigned to νM–O vibrations⁸.

Nuclear magnetic resonance spectra :

¹H NMR spectra of the mixed ligand complexes of Mg^{II} were recorded in DMSO-*d*₆. In free 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde and salicylaldehyde the aldehydic CH proton gives a singlet at δ 10.20 and 9.70 ppm respectively, which is shifted upfield in the mixed ligand complex [Mg(5-NO₂sal)(sal)(H₂O)₂] and appears at δ 9.77 and 9.15 ppm respectively. This upfield shift of CH proton peak supports the coordination of the C=O group of these ligand moieties to the magnesium atom. In free 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde, salicylaldehyde and 2-hydroxyacetophenone the OH proton peak appears at δ 11.95, 11.06 and 12.40 ppm respectively. This

Note

peak disappears in the mixed ligand complexes of Mg^{II} with these ligands indicating the formation of $Mg-O$ bond with the phenolic oxygen of these ligands through replacement of hydrogen of OH group. NMR spectrum of free 2-hydroxyacetophenone exhibits a singlet at δ 2.46 ppm due to CH_3 protons which is shifted upfield (δ 1.71 ppm) in the mixed ligand complex $[Mg(5-NO_2sal)(hap)(H_2O)_2]$. Up-field shift of this peak in the mixed ligand complex confirms the coordination of $C=O$ group to the metal atom. In 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde aromatic protons appear at δ 7.15 ppm (CH^a), δ 8.34 ppm (CH^b) and δ 8.40 ppm (CH^c) respectively. In the mixed ligand complexes $[Mg(5-NO_2sal)(sal)(H_2O)_2]$ and $[Mg(5-NO_2sal)(hap)(H_2O)_2]$, CH^a protons of 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde moiety appear as a doublet at δ 6.34 and 6.19 ppm, CH^b protons as a doublet at δ 7.81 and 7.81 ppm and CH^c protons as a singlet at δ 8.27 and 8.24 ppm respectively. Peaks due to aromatic protons of salicylaldehyde and 2-hydroxyacetophenone moieties appear as multiplets in the region δ 6.34–7.12 ppm. Thus the NMR spectra confirm the proposed structures of the mixed ligand complexes.

Experimental

Salicylaldehyde (E. Merck), 2-hydroxyacetophenone (John Baker), 2-hydroxypropiophenone (Fluka), 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde (Aldrich) and ethanol were purified by distillation. $MgCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (Merck), $CaCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ (Merck), $SrCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (Merck) and $BaCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ (Merck) were of A.R. grade.

Analytical methods : Magnesium, calcium and strontium were determined volumetrically by EDTA and barium gravimetrically as barium sulphate. Carbon and hydrogen analyses were carried out on a Heraeus Carlo Erba 1108 instrument and nitrogen was determined by Kjeldahl's method. Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded in the region $400-4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ on a Nicolet Magna-550 FT IR spectrophotometer. 1H NMR spectra were recorded in $DMSO-d_6$ using TMS as a reference on a Bruker 300 and Joel FX 90 Q FT NMR spectrometers.

Synthesis of mixed ligand complexes : To the ethanolic

solution of metal chloride (0.67 mmol, 0.1698 g in 2 ml of ethanol) an ethanolic solution of 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde (0.67 mmol, 0.1123 g in 2 ml of ethanol) and hydroxy-aromatic aldehyde or ketone (0.67 mmol in 2 ml of ethanol) were added. The pH of the resulting solution was raised to $\sim 10-10.5$ by adding 2% NaOH solution (~ 2 ml) dropwise with constant stirring. After stirring for 3–4 h the resulting yellow solid was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure.

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